

EFFECT OF SIZING ON THE INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER/BMI UNDER DIFFERENT PROCESSING TEMPERATURE

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Abstract: This paper aims to study impact of sizing on the interfacial properties of two T700 grade carbon fibers with bismaleimide (BMI), with the composites fabricated by different processing temperatures. Effect of sizing on the fiber surface properties, including fiber surface morphology and roughness, was analyzed. The sizing agent was extracted and it proved that the sizing content changed with the heat treatment temperatures on the carbon fiber. The results suggest that sizing content decreases with increasing treatment temperature, especially after 170 °C and 200 °C treatment. Functional groups of the extracted sizing and the mixture of sizing and BMI resin were investigated by FTIR. It demonstrates that the sizing is chemically reactive at 200 °C, and chemical reactions can take place between the fiber sizing and BMI at 170 °C. In addition, different diffusion, cure, and post-cure processing temperatures were conducted on the carbon fiber/BMI composites. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of the two composites shows the lowest values for the temperature scheme (without post-cure stage). However, no significant difference can be observed from the IFSS values of CF1/BMI and CF2/BMI composites, which were fabricated by with/without diffusion stage and different diffusion temperatures at 110 °C or 140 °C, respectively. Comparing the two composites, CF1/BMI always presents higher interfacial strength

than CF2/BMI, which is consistent with the degree of reactions between its fiber sizing and BMI. This indicates that the interfacial chemical bonding plays a key role in the interfacial strength of the carbon fiber/BMI composites.

1 Introduction

Carbon fibers have been studied and used extensively in an effort to utilise to the full potential advantages of its high specific strength and stiffness, lower density and flexible designs in composites technology [1-3]. It has been recognised that the composites performance of the play is dependent on the interphase formed between fiber and resin used, not only their own performances [4]. Thus, many efforts to improve the interfacial properties, such as surface treatments on carbon fiber, including plasma surface etching, chemical oxidation, irradiation treatment and sizing agents, have been made[5-9]. Sizing agents are the relatively easy and feasible way.

Sizing agents are always coated on the fiber surface during manufacturing [10, 11], and due to its particular position located between the fiber-matrix, it will definitely exert an impact on the interphase during the manufacturing process of composite as well as the formation of the nanoscale interphase. At present, open literatures concerning the effect of

sizing on interface most concentrate on particular processing conditions, rather than under different processing steps. Such as A. Paipetis and C. Galiotis found that the interfacial shear strength of the sized M40B system was consistently higher than that of the unsized system, and the interfacial failure of the sized system consists mainly of mixed-mode cracking, whereas clear fiber/matrix debonding was observed in the unsized system [12]. D. Upadhyaya et al. [13] showed that there existed a proper sizing level (0.7wt %) that yielded maximum short-beam and transverse flexural strengths for XAS carbon fiber/Epon 828 epoxy composite system. The polymer sizing provides the glass fiber with significantly improved both interfacial adhesion and fatigue properties as proved by Edith Mader [14].

Thus, study the effect of sizing on interfacial adhesion properties concerning the processing temperatures is of great significance. Z.S. Dai, et al. showed that the interfacial shear strength of the heat treated carbon fiber/epoxy is lower than that of the untreated [15]. Guo et al. indicated that the physico-chemical interactions of carbon fiber and the epoxy sizing had a significant effect on the strength of the carbon fibers with the increasing heat-treatment temperature [10].

In this paper, the impact of sizing on the interfacial properties of two T700 grade carbon fibers with bismaleimide (BMI) fabricated by different processing temperatures are analyzed. Firstly, Atomic force microscope (AFM) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) were employed to analyze the fiber surface roughness and the chemical properties before and after the sizing extraction. The wetting behavior between the carbon fibers and the resin was tested at elevated temperature. Moreover, the chemical reactivity of the sizing agents and chemical reactions of typical functional groups in sizing agents/BMI mixtures were proved by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Two kinds of T700 grade high strength carbon fibers (CF1 and CF2 for short) were used in this study, supplied by Beijing Institute of Aeronautic Materials (BIAM), China. Soxhlet method was used to extract sizing agent from fiber surface, which was conducted by acetone at 80°C for 24h with about 20m fiber in length. The fiber after sizing removal was marked as desized-carbon fiber (e.g. desized-CF1) and the extracted sizing agent was designated as Carbon Fiber-sizing (e.g. CF1-sizing).

Resin used in this research is an allyl bisphenol A modified bismaleimide (BMI), supplied by Chinese Academy of Sciences. The standard cure schedule of BMI is 1h at 140°C, 2h at 170°C and 4h at 200°C.

2.2 Characterization

2.2.1 Surface morphology and roughness

Surface morphology was examined with a CamScan-Apollo300 scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at 20KV.

AFM observations of carbon fibers were carried out in tapping mode with a scanning region of 5 μ m \times 5 μ m, using a dimension icon atomic force microscope made in American Veeco Corporation. Surface roughness was calculated via NanoScope Analysis Software, and at least 20 valid data were applied for each specimen.

2.2.2 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

Measurements were made using a ESCALab220i-XL (VG Scientific) equipped with a Monochromated Al K α x-ray source at 300W in an evacuated chamber at 3 \times 10⁻⁹ mbar. Peak binding energies were calibrated upon C1s peak at 284.8eV. A seven-parameter curve fitting was made for the C1s spectra using XPSPEAK software and the content of activated carbon atoms was calculated according to the sub-peak integral area.

2.2.3 Wetting behavior

A dynamic contact angle and surface/interfacial tension instrument (DCAT21, Dataphysics) was adopted for the measurement of advancing contact angles between resin and single fibers. Five monofilaments were tested at the same time with the immersion speed of 0.01mm/s, surface detection threshold of 0.15 mg and immersion depth of 3mm. The experiment was carried out with five monofilaments tested at the same time, and each test repeated at least five times.

2.2.4 Infrared spectroscopy (IR)

FTIR spectroscopy (Nicolet Nexus 470) was applied to evaluate the functional groups in sizing agents and resins. The chemical interaction was estimated by concentration changes of the functional groups before and after heat treatment. The peak at 830 cm^{-1} was selected as the reference peak due to little interference and appropriate peak intensity. The concentration of functional groups was calculated by the ratio of the characteristic peak and the reference peak.

2.2.5 Interfacial shear strength (IFSS)

Micro-droplet method was used to evaluate the IFSSs of carbon fiber reinforced BMI composites on a machine (MODEL HM410) from Japan was used at the sensitivity of 1/100gf with moving speed of 0.03mm/min. The matrix resin was wetted onto a carbon fiber filament to form a micro-droplet surrounding the fiber diameter due to the function of surface tension. After resin cure in oven, the single fiber was fixed on a concave mold. The knives came in contact with the solid resin droplet and the force required to debond the droplet from the fiber was recorded. The IFSS, τ was consequently calculated from: $\tau = F_{max}/\pi dl$, where F_{max} is the maximum load, d the fiber diameter and l the embedded length. At least 15 valid data were taken for each system.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Sizing agents of fibers

Fig.1 FTIR spectra of sizing agents

Chemical properties of CF1-sizing and CF2-sizing were conducted by FTIR in Fig.1, both sizing shows similar functional groups, such as epoxide group at 915 cm^{-1} , hydroxyl at 3440 cm^{-1} , carbonyl at 1710 cm^{-1} , benzene (1510 cm^{-1} and 1610 cm^{-1}), ether at 1043 cm^{-1} and the vibrations of C-H of para-benzene at 829 cm^{-1} . From FTIR spectra, one thing is known that the main constituent in both sizings are epoxy type.

Fig.2 The relative concentration of typical functional groups of: (a) CF1-sizing; and (b) CF2-sizing, before and after 200 °C treatment for 2h

To investigate chemical reaction capabilities of the extracted sizings, 200 °C was chosen on the basis of curing process of resin, and the functional groups variations were shown in Fig.2. Concentration of epoxide groups decreases and hydroxyl groups increases of both sizings after heat treatment, but those of CF1-sizing show prominent change degree when compared with CF2-sizing. And, C=O and ether groups increase in CF1-sizing, while the opposite trend is for CF2-sizing. The results indicate that CF1-sizing is of higher activity at 200 °C due to the relatively full reaction. Moreover, C-H vibration of C=C at 3099 cm^{-1} is found only in CF1-sizing, which vanishes after heat treatment. Because of such high reactivity at 200 °C, the change of extracted sizing content of CF1 with the rising temperatures was further conducted, shown in Fig.3. Almost no changes of extracted sizing content is observed until the CF1 was treated at 130 °C for 2h, indicating the initiation of reaction of sizing itself or the reaction between sizing and the functional groups on fiber surface. The most obvious decline in compared with the sizing extracted content at room temperature is at 200 °C, which also proves the chemical reactivity of CF1-sizing.

Fig.3 The extracted sizing content of CF1 after different heat-treatments for 2h

3.2 Properties of fiber surface

Fig.4 Fiber surface of: (a) CF1, (b) CF2, Ra means surface roughness of carbon fiber

SEM and AFM were employed to characterize the surface morphology of the carbon fibers, as shown in Fig.4. There are shades of grooves along the fiber axis on both fiber surfaces, but great difference exists in the surface morphology from AFM results. CF1 shows wavy and compact grooves with well-distributed sizing agent, however, CF2 shows uniform grooves with unevenly distributed sizing agents, which make the surface roughness (Ra) higher than that of CF1.

The contact angles, tested by DCAT at 80°, were shown in Fig.5. The contact angle between CF1 and BMI was 74°±1°, while 76°±2° for CF2 and BMI. Both sized fibers have similar wettability with BMI resin, which may be ascribed to the similar compositions of sizings. However, the contact angles between carbon fibers after sizing removal and BMI are lower than those of sized ones, indicating that sizing agents go against the wetting behavior carbon fiber and BMI matrix.

Fig.5 Dynamic contact angles (°) of carbon fibers with BMI at 80°C

To understand the chemistry of fiber surface, a seven-parameter curve fitting was conducted for the C1s spectra by taking 284.8 eV as the reference peak using XPSPEAK, the activated carbon content are defined as carbon in combination with O or N, i.e. the groups of C-OH, C-O-C, C-NH₂, epoxide, C-O-C=O, -COOH, and -COOR for peak3-peak7. As can be seen in Table1, percentage of activated carbon content on desized-CF1 is slightly higher than that of the CF1, while 3% content reduction was observed on the desized-CF2. Sizing agent cannot be absolutely removed by acetone extraction. This could be resulted from possible reactions between the sizing components and/or between the sizing and active chemical groups at the pristine carbon fiber surface, generated by electrolytic treatment during the fiber fabrication process. Thus, content of activated carbon of desized fibers may be influenced both by the residues of the sizing agent and the

pristine carbon fiber. However, it's worth noting that the content of peak 4 (C-O-C=O and epoxide) in CF1, that involved in the chemical reaction between sizing agent and BMI, is higher than that in CF2. That's may be one reason caused better interfacial adhesion of CF1/BMI when comparing with CF2/BMI. In addition, the contents of -C=O, -O-C=O and HO-C=O on two fibers basically appeared after sizing removal, the reason for this variation might lie in the acid oxidation process before coating during the manufacture of carbon fibers. To sum up, sizing agent can alter the chemical properties of fiber, which will further affect the composite behavior.

Table 1 XPS results of peak resolving

No. [⊕]	Peak position n/g [⊕]	Peak assignment [⊕]	CF1 [⊕]	desized-CF1 [⊕]	CF2 [⊕]	Desized-CF2 [⊕]
Peak 1 [⊕]	284.8 [⊕]	Reference [⊕]	53.33 [⊕]	0 [⊕]	18.37 [⊕]	39.28 [⊕]
Peak 2 [⊕]	285 [⊕]	-C-C [⊕] -C-H [⊕]	20.75 [⊕]	73.04 [⊕]	45.91 [⊕]	28 [⊕]
Peak 3 [⊕]	286.1 [⊕]	-C-OH [⊕] -C-O [⊕] -C-NH ₂ [⊕]	1.41 [⊕]	3.64 [⊕]	17.72 [⊕]	19.43 [⊕]
Peak 4 [⊕]	286.6 [⊕]	C-O-C=O [⊕] Epoxide [⊕]	24.51 [⊕]	18.29 [⊕]	16.39 [⊕]	5.99 [⊕]
Peak 5 [⊕]	287.7 [⊕]	-C=O [⊕] -C=N [⊕]	— [⊕]	2.60 [⊕]	0 [⊕]	3.00 [⊕]
Peak 6 [⊕]	289.4 [⊕]	-O-C=O [⊕] HO-C=O [⊕]	— [⊕]	2.42 [⊕]	0.82 [⊕]	3.41 [⊕]
Peak 7 [⊕]	290.6 [⊕]	-COO [⊕] π-π* [⊕]	— [⊕]	— [⊕]	0.69 [⊕]	0.89 [⊕]
Activated carbon/% [⊕]	— [⊕]	— [⊕]	25.92 [⊕]	26.95 [⊕]	35.72 [⊕]	32.72 [⊕]

3.3 Sizing effect on interfacial adhesion of carbon fiber/BMI

To investigate the sizing effect on interfacial properties of carbon fiber composites under different processing temperatures, four temperature schemes were designed according to the standard schedule of 140°C 1h+170°C 2h+200°C 4h (scheme D in Fig.6), which can be divided into three stages, that is the diffusion stage(140°C 1h), the cure stage (170°C 2h), and the post-cure stage (200°C 4h). The other three

processing schemes are 140°C 1h+170°C 2h (A) without post-cure stage, 170°C 2h+200°C 4h (B) without diffusion stage and 110°C 1h+170°C 2h+200°C 4h (C), respectively. The corresponding resin curing degree for scheme A, B, C and D are 84.9%, 98%, 95.4% and 96.7% for the BMI matrix.

Fig.6 shows the variations of interfacial shear strengths against processing temperatures. IFSSs of the two composites show the lowest values for the scheme A with the minimum resin cure degree. The IFSS values of the other three schemes (B, C and D) of CF1/BMI steadily increase from 66.45 to 77.34MPa, which agrees well with the increasing cure degree of the BMI matrix. However, such tendency has not been found in CF1/BMI. Considering coefficient of dispersion, no significant difference can be observed from the IFSS values of schemes B, C and D for the same carbon fiber composite. This indicates that the diffusion stage and the diffusion temperatures (at 110°C or 140°C) have no significant effect on the interfacial properties of CF1/BMI and CF2/BMI.

Comparing the IFSSs of CF1/BMI and CF2/BMI under the same temperature schemes, the former one always presents higher IFSS values than the latter.

Fig.6 Interfacial shear strengths of CF1/BMI and CF2/BMI, which was fabricated by different temperature schemes: A, 140°C 1h+170°C 2h; B, 170°C 2h+200°C 4h; C, 110°C 1h+170°C 2h+200°C 4h; and D, 140°C 1h+170°C 2h+200°C 4h

3.4 Chemical reaction between sizing and resin

FTIR was employed to study the chemical reactions between sizings and BMI, the mixtures of sizing and BMI were treated at 170 °C for 2h by taking consideration of the cure schedule of BMI. The concentration change of the functional groups can be seen in Fig.7.

Fig.7 The relative concentration of typical functional groups of: (a) CF1-sizing/BMI mixture; and (b) CF2-sizing/BMI mixture, before and after 170°C treatment for 2h

The concentrations of epoxide group and C=CH decrease, accompanying with considerable increasing hydroxyl group after 170 °C treatment can be seen in Fig.7 (a). This result indicates that incomplete chemical reaction taken place in CF1-sizing/BMI mixture, since epoxide and C=CH groups are main reaction groups to be speculated according to the possible reaction mechanism. However, epoxide group shows little variation and content of C=CH increases after heat-treatment,

suggesting a lower degree of chemical reaction in CF2-sizing/BMI, as shown in Fig. 7(b). This explains the result that CF1/BMI composites always present higher interfacial properties than CF2/BMI, regardless of the processing temperature schemes.

4 Conclusions

The purpose of this study is to discuss the impact of sizing on the interfacial properties of two T700 grade carbon fibers with BMI under different processing temperatures. FTIR analysis indicates the two extracted sizing agents both contain epoxy constituent and have chemical reactivity at 200°C, in which CF1-sizing is higher active. AFM and XPS tests indicate that sizing agent can modify the surface roughness and the activated carbon content and change functional contents. Moreover, the desized carbon fibers show better wetting property with BMI resin than the sized fiber, respectively. However, comparing the degree of chemical reactions between sizing agent and BMI, the results suggest that chemical reactions taken place between them is conducive to the improving the interfacial strength of carbon fiber/BMI, and the higher degree of reactions, the higher interfacial adhesion of the composite. In addition, the results show that the diffusion stage and the diffusion temperatures (at 110°C or 140°C) have no significant effect on the interfacial properties of CF1/BMI and CF2/BMI, while there is a certain relationship between IFSS and the resin cure degree.

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